

Data analyses

To answer the research questions, we combined quantitative and qualitative analysis to examine the relationships between AWT-derived metrics, self-reported surveys, and employee well-being.

To address RQ1, which focuses on the correspondence between AWT-derived metrics and self-reported measures, multilevel analyses were conducted. The data consisted of repeated daily observations nested within individuals, requiring an approach that accounts for the non-independence of observations (Stawski, 2013). Although the QEEW items are ordinal (1-5 scale), they were treated as continuous to facilitate model comparison. To distinguish within-person from between-person effects, predictors were person-mean centered following Wang and Maxwell (2015). This approach isolates day-to-day deviations from an individual's typical behavior, such that the estimated effects reflect whether deviations in AWT metrics within a person are associated with a corresponding deviation in the self-reported survey. Model fit was reported using marginal R^2 (R^2_m), representing the variance explained by the fixed effects, and conditional R^2 (R^2_m), representing the variance explained by both fixed and random effects (Nakagawa & Schielzeth, 2013). For each survey item, matched AWT-derived metrics were entered simultaneously to estimate their unique contributions. Multicollinearity between predictors was assessed using variance inflation factors (VIF), which were all below 3, indicating that multicollinearity was not a concern for these analyses.

To interpret the quantitative findings of RQ1, qualitative follow-up interviews were analyzed. The interviews were used to identify aspects of work that were not captured by AWT data or were interpreted differently by participants. The eight transcripts of the 30-40 minute interviews were analyzed using an iterative deductive coding in NVivo³, where the topics of the surveys were used as main codes. Additional codes were added to differentiate what could and could not be found in the AWT data. The qualitative data was used to contextualize and interpret the results found in the multilevel analyses.

To address RQ2, which examines how AWT-derived metrics relate to well-being compared to self-report measures, regression analyses were conducted at the weekly level. Daily AWT metrics and self-report scores were aggregated and related to weekly measures of work engagement and exhaustion. Based on reliability analyses, items were combined into scales for contact possibilities ($\alpha = .83$), independence in work ($\alpha = .80$), and variety ($\alpha = .82$). Regression models were estimated in two steps: first, including only AWT-derived metrics, and subsequently adding self-report measurement to assess their additional explanatory variance.

In total, 238 daily observations were analyzed, nested within 15 participants, ranging from 12 to 23 days per participant ($M = 15.9$). Multilevel analyses were conducted to examine within-person associations between metrics derived from computer behavior and daily survey measures. The predictors were standardized (b) prior to analysis for better comparison across variables. Interpretation focused on statistical significance and the proportion of within-person variance explained by the model (marginal R^2 ; R^2_m). Tables 2 to 6 report the model results, including the within-person fixed coefficients (b), standard errors (SE), test statistics (t), and the p-value, with statistical significance indicated using asterisks.

Changes in Work

Computer Activity	Survey	b	SE	t
Ratio of new apps	C1: To what extent did significant changes occur in your work compared to the previous period?	0.005	0.065	0.08
Ratio of new window titles		-.029	0.065	-0.44

Table 2. Multilevel Analysis Changes in Work (* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, and *** $p < .001$).

No significant relations were found between AWT-derived metrics and perceived changes in work (Table 2). The explained variance was low ($R^2_m = 0.033$), indicating that AWT-derived metrics accounted for only 3.3% of day-to-day variation in perceived changes in work. The interview data suggest that this

³ NVivo 14. Lumivero (2023)

divergence relates to differences in temporal reference frame. Within the five-week observation window, the AWT correctly classified certain activities as new, as they had not appeared before in the captured data. However, participants evaluated change against their broader work cycle, drawing on knowledge that extended beyond the observation period. An illustrative example is grading exams: the AWT registered this as a new activity within the study window, while participants recognized it as an annually recurring task. The behavioral and subjective measures thus operated on different temporal horizons, with the AWT constrained to the observation period and self-report drawing on a longer work history.

Despite the absence of significant group-level associations, exploratory analyses reveal substantial variability across individuals. For example, for one participant (P19, $n = 23$ days), there was a moderate negative relationship between ratio of new window titles and the perceived changes in work ($\beta = -.35$), where for another participant (P2, $n = 15$) there was a moderate positive correlation ($\beta = .35$). While the AWT-derived metrics do not consistently capture perceived changes in work across participants, they may still reflect meaningful variation for individuals.

Contact Possibilities

Computer Activity	Survey	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t</i>
Count of idle events	CP1: To what extent were you able to leave your work area to chat with a colleague?	0.076	0.079	0.97
Count of collaborative apps	CP2: To what extent did you have contact with colleagues as part of your work?	0.036	0.101	0.35
Duration of collaborative apps		-.033	0.101	-0.44
Ratio of collaborative work	CP3: To what extent were you able to chat with colleagues during working hours?	0.037	0.074	0.50

Table 3. Multilevel Analysis Contact Possibilities (* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, and *** $p < .001$).

Across all three items (CP1-CP3), no significant associations were observed with the corresponding AWT-derived metrics (Table 3). The within-person explained variance was limited across the three models, suggesting that the AWT-derived metrics provided little information about day-to-day variation in perceived contact possibilities.

The interviews help explain this divergence. First, contact with colleagues frequently occurred away from the computer, through in-person conversation, reading, or work on untracked devices, meaning that idle periods in the AWT data did not always correspond to opportunities for colleague interaction. Second, participants interpreted contact possibilities broadly, encompassing informal and non-work-related conversations in addition to digital collaboration. The current AWT metrics captured the use of collaborative applications, but not the nature or purpose of the interactions occurring within them.

Exploratory individual-level analyses showed variations between participants. For example, the relationship between duration of collaborative applications and perceived contact possibilities was moderately positive for P7 ($\beta = .48$, $n = 18$), but negative for P5 ($\beta = -.29$, $n = 19$). Similarly, the relationship between the *ratio of collaborative work* showed a moderate positive correlation for P7 ($\beta = .28$, $n = 18$), and a moderate negative correlation for P2 ($\beta = -.31$, $n = 15$). These findings suggest that behavioral computer activity may relate differently to perceived contact possibilities depending on participants' work practices, such as whether collaboration primarily occurs digitally or in person, or whether someone uses the computer during meetings or takes notes on paper.

Independence in Work

Computer Activity	Survey	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t</i>
Count of idle events	I5: To what extent were you able to interrupt your work for a short time when you felt it was necessary?	0.077	0.089	0.86
Average duration of idle events		-0.022	0.086	-.025
Ratio of idle duration		0.038	0.098	0.39
Ratio of idle time		-0.117	0.098	-1.20

Standard deviation of app duration	I8: To what extent could you personally decide how much time you need for a specific activity?	-0.227***	0.067	-3.40
Standard deviation of session duration		0.086	0.067	1.28
Deviation in schedule	I10: To what extent could you organize your work yourself?	-0.021	0.065	-.033

Table 4. Multilevel Analysis Independence in Work (*p < .05, ** p < .01, and *** p < .001).

For independence in work, most AWT-derived metrics were not significantly related to the matched questionnaire items (Table 4). The exception was the *standard deviation of app duration*, which was negatively related to the I8 self-report survey item ($R^2_m = .040$). Interview data shed light on the pattern of non-significant results for the remaining metrics. Participants described many periods of computer inactivity as work-related and sometimes unavoidable, including attending meetings, carrying out educational tasks, and taking notes. One participant described the writing process as involving work both on and off the screen, indicating that idle time in the AWT data did not straightforwardly correspond to deliberate breaks from work. A similar pattern emerged for schedule deviation: obligatory meetings and external commitments could constrain perceived independence even when observed start and end times remained close to an individual's typical schedule. The behavioral and subjective measures thus captured different aspects of independence, with AWT reflecting observable patterns of application use and timing, and self-report reflecting the experienced degree of autonomy over work.

Work Variety

Computer Activity	Survey	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t</i>
Ratio of new window titles	V1: To what extent did you have to do the same things repeatedly in your work?	-0.018	0.062	-0.29
Count of app switches		0.146*	0.062	2.35
Count of unique app categories	V3: To what extent was your work varied?	0.068	0.071	0.96
Count of unique apps	V2: To what extent was your work varied?	-0.027	0.071	-.038
Count of app switches	V6: To what extent did your work have enough variety in your work?	-.266*	0.124	-2.14
Count of app category switches		0.250*	0.124	2.01

Table 5. Multilevel Analysis Work Variety (*p < .05, ** p < .01, and *** p < .001).

Results for work variety were mixed (Table 5). No significant relationships were found for *ratio of new window titles*, *count of unique app categories*, and *count of unique apps*. However, *Count of app switches* was significantly positively related to perceived work variety for both item V1, $b = 0.146$, $SE = 0.062$, $t(229.4) = 2.35$, $p = .020$, and item V6, $b = -.266$, $SE = 0.124$, $t(229.4) = -2.14$, $p = .034$. Count of app category switches was significantly positively related to perceived work variety item V6, $b = 0.250$, $SE = 0.124$, $t(229.4) = 2.01$, $p = .045$. The interview data suggest that app switching may capture negative variety rather than experienced variety. Participants indicated that multiple small tasks could be experienced as one larger, unpleasant block of work rather than as true variation. However, switching between app categories may better reflect movement between different types of activities, which is closer to how participants interpreted variety. Thus, the results indicate partial alignment, but also show that behavioral and subjective measures capture different facets of work variety.

Remaining Work Characteristics

Computer Activity	Survey	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t</i>
Usage during off hours	R1: To what extent did you work overtime?	0.250***	0.056	4.42
Average duration of sessions	R6: To what extent were you able to complete tasks without being interrupted?	0.088	0.059	1.48

Duration of longest session		0.004	0.057	0.07
Ratio of sessions		-.002	0.056	-0.03
Ratio of window revisits after idle time	R9: To what extent did you experience disruptions while working?	-0.124*	0.053	-2.32
Deviation of start time	R13: To what extent could you determine your own start and finish times of your work day?	-0.081	0.067	-1.20
Deviation of end time		0.017	0.067	0.26
Table 6. Multilevel Analysis Remaining Questions about Work (*p < .05, ** p < .01, and *** p < .001).				

For working overtime (R6), off-hour computer usage was strongly and positively related to self-report item R1, $b = 0.250$, $SE = 0.056$, $t(228.3) = 4.42$, $p < .001$, with relatively high within-person explained variance ($R^2_m = 0.120$; Table 6).

For experienced disruptions, *ratio of window revisits after idle time* was negatively related to perceived disruptions, $b = -0.124$, $SE = 0.053$, $t() = -2.32$, $R^2_m = 0.022$. Participants indicated in the interview that this pattern reflects the fact that idle periods were sometimes productive rather than disruptive. Participants described talking to colleagues, thinking, or taking notes before returning to the same window, meaning revisiting a window after idle time did not necessarily imply that work had been disrupted.

No significant relationships were found for the ability to complete tasks without interruption ($R^2_m = 0.098$) or for control over start and finish times ($R^2_m = 0.052$). Interviews pointed to the limits of the AWT metrics for capturing the meaning of these constructs. Participants described interruptions in computer use that were part of continuing the same task. Moreover, flexibility in start and finish times was not only about observed timing, but also about whether the day was perceived as self-directed. Some participants mentioned a decreased feeling of control when they had an obligatory meeting at the start of the day, even if that would not affect when they would typically have started their day. These findings suggest divergence between the behavioral and subjective measures for these items.

The Relation between Computer Activity, Survey Measures, and Well-Being

To examine the extent to which metrics derived from computer activity relate to well-being compared to traditional self-report surveys (RQ2), a series of regression models was estimated at the weekly level. For each construct, a model including AWT-derived metrics was compared with a second model that additionally included the corresponding survey measures. This allowed us to assess both the explained variance of AWT-derived metrics and the incremental contribution of the self-report surveys.

Work Engagement

Computer Activity	Survey	R^2 (AWT)	R^2 (AWT + QEEW)	ΔR^2
Ratio of new apps Ratio of new window titles	Changes in tasks	.001	.032	.031
Count of idle events Count of collaborative apps Duration of collaborative apps Ratio of collaborative work	Contact Possibilities	.086	.086	0
Count of idle events Average duration of idle events	Independence in Work***	.228	.379	.151***

Ratio of idle duration				
Standard deviation of app duration				
Standard deviation of session duration*				
Deviation in schedule				
Ratio of new window titles	Work Variety*	.154	.231	.077*
Count of app switches				
Count of unique app categories				
Count of unique apps				
Count of app category switches				
Usage during off-hours	Working overtime	.002	.004	.002
Average duration of sessions	Completing tasks	.238	.259	.021
Duration longest session**				
Ratio of sessions**				
Average duration of sessions	Disruptions	.045	.048	.003
Deviation of start time	Control end and finish times*	.074	.137	.063*
Deviation of end time*				
Table 7. Model Comparison for Work Engagement				

Table 7 presents regression results for weekly work engagement. For *changes in tasks*, *contact possibilities*, *working overtime*, *completing tasks*, and *disruptions*, no significant relationships were observed for either the AWT-derived metrics or the self-report surveys. However, three constructs stand out.

For *independence in work*, the *standard deviation of session duration* was significantly negatively related to work engagement, $b = -.005$, $SE = 0.002$, $t(54) = -2.17$, $p = .035$, $\beta = -.37$., whereas the self-report scale was significantly positively related to work engagement, $b = 0.326$, $SE = 0.090$, $t(54) = 3.63$, $p < .001$, $\beta = .42$. The model, including the self-report, explained 15.1% more variance than the model with only the AWT-derived metrics ($R^2 = .379$). This suggests that AWT-derived metrics capture behavioral aspects related to independence of work and self-report provides complementary information about the subjective experience.

For *work variety*, no AWT-derived metrics were found to be significant. However, the self-report survey scale was found to be significantly positively related to work engagement, $b = 0.282$, $SE = 0.120$, $t(55) = 2.35$, $p = .022$, $\beta = .29$. This suggests divergence between behavioral and self-report measures for this construct when investigating work engagement.

For *control over start and finish times*, the deviation of end time was found to be significantly negatively related to work engagement, $b = -0.002$, $SE = 0.001$, $t(58) = -2.52$, $p = .015$, $\beta = .35$, while the self-report survey was found to be significantly positively related to work engagement, $b = 0.176$, $SE = 0.085$, $t(58) = 2.06$, $p = .044$, $\beta = .26$. The significant change of 6.3% change in explained variance ($R^2 = .137$), indicates that AWT-derived metrics capture certain behavioral aspects related to control over end and finish times, but not the full subjective experience measured with the self-report survey. The two approaches appear complementary rather than interchangeable.

Exhaustion

Computer Activity	Survey	R ² (AWT)	R ² (AWT + QEEW)	ΔR ²
Ratio of new apps	Changes in tasks	.097	.117	.020
Ratio of new window titles				

Count of idle events Count of collaborative apps Duration of collaborative apps** Ratio of collaborative work	Contact Possibilities	.206	.228	.022
Count of idle events Average duration of idle events Ratio of idle duration Standard deviation of app duration Standard deviation of session duration Deviation in schedule**	Independence in Work*	.203	.289	.086*
Ratio of new window titles Count of app switches** Count of unique app categories* Count of unique apps Count of app category switches**	Work Variety*	.206	.277	.070*
Usage during off-hours**	Working overtime	.125	.156	.031
Average duration of sessions Duration longest session Ratio of sessions	Completing tasks*	.143	.209	.066*
Ratio of window revisits after idle time	Disruptions	.072	.085	.012
Deviation of start time Deviation of end time**	Control start and finish times**	.124	.247	.123**
Table 8. Model Comparison for Exhaustion				

Table 8 shows the regression results examining weekly exhaustion. For *changes in tasks and disruptions*, no significant relations were found with exhaustion. Adding self-report did not significantly improve the explained variance.

For *contact possibilities*, *duration of collaborative apps* was found to be significantly positively correlated to exhaustion, $b = 0.017$, $SE = 0.005$, $t(56) = 3.19$, $p = .002$, $\beta = .57$, while the self-report survey scale was not found to be significant and did not improve model fit. This suggests that.

For *independence in work*, the deviation in schedule was found to be significant, $b = 0.005$, $SE = 0.002$, $t(54) = 2.79$, $p = .007$, $\beta = .39$, as well as the self-report scale, $b = -0.371$, $SE = 0.145$, $t(54) = -2.56$, $p = .013$, $\beta = -.32$, although in opposite directions. The model, including the self-report survey scale, explained 8.6% more variance ($R^2 = .289$). This suggests that the two measures capture different aspects of independence in work and provide complementary information.

For *work variety*, three AWT-derived metrics were found to be significant. First, *count of app switches* was positively related to exhaustion, $b = 0.006$, $SE = 0.002$, $t(55) = 2.79$, $p = .007$, $\beta = .82$. Second, *count of unique app categories* was found positively related to exhaustion, $b = 0.206$, $SE = 0.086$, $t(55) = 2.39$, $p = .020$, $\beta = .34$. And last, *count of app category switches* was found negatively related to exhaustion, $b = -.006$, $SE = 0.002$, $t(55) = -2.76$, $p = .008$, $\beta = -.77$. The self-report scale for work variation was also found significantly negatively correlated with exhaustion, $b = -.404$, $SE = 0.175$, $t(55) = -2.31$, $p = .024$, $\beta = -.28$, and added 7.0% additional explained variance to the model ($R^2 = .277$). Together, these findings suggest partial overlap between the behavioral and subjective measures due to correlations between the predictors, but also indicate that they capture different aspects of work variety and therefore provide complementary information.

For *completing tasks*, only the self-report survey was significantly related to exhaustion, $b = -0.434$, $SE = 0.199$, $t(57) = -2.18$, $p = .033$, $\beta = -.27$. With an additional 6.6% variance explained ($R^2 = .209$), this

indicates that the subjective experience of being able to complete tasks without interruption was relevant for exhaustion, whereas the matched behavioral metrics were not.

For *control start and finish*, both *deviation of end time*, $b = 0.003$, $SE = 0.001$, $t(58) = 3.13$, $p = .003$, $\beta = .40$, and the self-report survey item was significantly related to exhaustion, $b = -0.369$, $SE = 0.120$, $t(58) = -3.08$, $p = .003$, $\beta = -.36$. With an additional 12.3% explained variance ($R^2 = .247$), this suggests that both behavioral and subjective aspects of control over start and finish times of the work day contribute to explaining exhaustion, pointing to complementarity between the two measures.